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Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source

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Abstract

Energy is crucial in every aspect of our lives; without it, systems requiring energy would cease to function. This study was conducted by researchers not only to address the need for reducing carbon emissions but also to provide low-cost electricity. The Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source aims to offer a clean and sustainable energy solution, particularly for areas with insufficient energy supply. This innovative product utilizes various materials, such as a DC motor, solar charging module, battery, faucet, and electrical wire, to accumulate energy from water pressure. The study involved surveying 90 residents from Barangay Mapulang Lupa, Barangay Maysan, and Barangay Ugong in Valenzuela City, selected through purposive sampling. By employing a descriptive method through survey questionnaire, the researchers assessed the acceptability of the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source in terms of affordability, durability, functionality, and safety. The data were analyzed using frequency and mean. The results indicated that most respondents were between 18 and 30 years old. Considering their demographic profiles, the researchers concluded that the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source was well accepted by the respondents. This study highlights the potential of such innovations in providing sustainable and accessible energy solutions, contributing to both environmental sustainability and economic benefits for underserved areas. The maximum and fastest charging times for the water pressure-driven power source are as follows: for a 6-volt battery, 1 hour; for a 12-volt battery, 2 hours and 3 minutes; and for a 24-volt battery, 4 hours and 5 minutes, all at a PSI of 80 with an output voltage of 0.09 per minute.

Keywords: *water pressure, dynamo, Pounds per Square Inch (PSI), hydroelectricity, sustainable energy*

Introduction

The method of producing electricity from the energy of falling or flowing water is known as hydroelectricity. The turbine blades spin when water passes over them, which in turn powers a generator to generate energy. Because hydroelectric power depends on the natural water cycle and doesn't burn up resources or emit greenhouse gases when in use, it is a renewable energy source. Additionally, it contributes to energy security and sustainability and is a major component of the energy mix in many nations (International Hydropower Association, 2021).

Due to rising energy costs, balance of payment issues, and concerns about the reliability of energy supplies, many countries are reconsidering the role of hydroelectric power in their national energy strategies. Since hydroelectric generation does not use up water, these projects, once established, can also support agricultural and industrial development, addressing two significant challenges in developing countries. While, most hydroelectric projects have had positive outcomes, they have also led to notable negative environmental impacts. Two key issues are highlighted: the challenges posed by erosion and sediment buildup, and the consequences of flooding, particularly regarding the relocation of affected populations (Biswas, 2010).

The social and environmental effects of massive hydroelectric projects on communities and ecosystems are a local issue related to hydroelectricity in the Philippines. The Casecan Hydroelectric Project in Nueva Ecija is a noteworthy example, as it has encountered problems with the uprooting of indigenous villages, deforestation, and biodiversity threats. Farmers downstream who rely on the river for irrigation have been impacted by the project's water use conflicts. Furthermore, river ecosystems are frequently altered as a result of the environmental changes brought about by dams, which can be detrimental to fish populations and aquatic biodiversity. Concerns have also been expressed by indigenous groups, mainly the Bugkalot tribe, on how these projects may affect their ancestral lands and resources (Cruz et al., 2016).

The researchers undertook this study to deliver a sustainable and accessible energy source for communities, particularly those in remote areas lacking electricity. By leveraging improvised water pressure-driven power systems, this innovation aims to meet the increasing global demand for clean energy and reduce reliance on fossil fuels, thereby contributing to climate change mitigation.

Furthermore, this research addresses the growing issue of electronic waste management by providing an eco-friendly solution for recycling materials to develop a unique product that harnesses renewable energy (Goyal, 2023). Such a system could be implemented in locations with limited access to large water bodies, enhancing the accessibility of hydroelectric power. Additionally, it has the potential to improve energy reliability in regions facing frequent power shortages while minimizing environmental impacts. Given that water pressure is readily available in households, the researchers sought to utilize this pressure as a viable source for hydroelectricity generation.

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the voltage output of the Water Pressure-Driven Power Source on the following pounds per square inch (PSI)?
 - 1.1. 20;
 - 1.2. 30;
 - 1.3. 40;
 - 1.4. 50;
 - 1.5. 60;
 - 1.6. 70; and
 - 1.7. 80?
2. How long does the Water Pressure- Driven Power Source fully charge the following batteries?
 - 2.1. 6v;
 - 2.2. 12v; and
 - 2.3. 24v?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. affordability;
 - 3.2. durability;
 - 3.3. functionality; and
 - 3.4. safety?

Literature Review

The studies conducted by Ghisi (2019) and Lamberts (2014) examined how adjusting the flow rate of electric showers can affect temperature, providing flow rates comparable to those of gas heating systems. Similarly, the research by Soito and Freitas (2016), along with Jawahar and Michael (2017), suggests that microscale hydropower systems utilize the potential energy stored in reservoirs to mitigate the intermittent nature of solar and wind energy. This approach is highlighted as a cost-effective and space-efficient option for electricity generation.

Furthermore, Kaunda (2014) noted that hydropower generation depends on the movement of water across a specific head differential, which generates energy. Kusre (2015) and Bayazt (2017) found that estimating theoretical hydropower potential involves factors such as flow rate and height variation of falling water over a defined period. Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques have been used to identify potential sites for small-scale hydropower projects and assess their power capacity.

Tahseen et al. (2017) emphasized that while hydropower offers potential for pollution reduction, it also presents challenges, including environmental disruptions and safety risks. Gonzales (2015) pointed out that shower heads can provide benefits like improved water pressure, conservation, and versatile applications in both technical and experimental contexts.

The functionality of hydroelectricity illustrated by Blokker (2010), Ilha et al. (2014), and Goncalves (2016) indicates that the design of water supply pipelines should account for the highest observed flows and planned rates to avoid oversized pipelines, which can result in inefficiencies. Managing excessive flow rates is critical for rational water use, particularly in lavatories that tend to have high water consumption and leakage. Even water-saving hydro-mechanical fixtures necessitate regular maintenance to avoid potential issues, ensuring their continued functionality and efficiency.

Additionally, Li (2018) introduced a hydropower generator featuring a spiral-shaped turbine within a shower head, capable of producing up to 8 W of power, making it suitable for recharging small batteries or phones. Hydropower is praised for its global availability, excellent energy conversion efficiency, minimal running costs, and relatively long lifespan. Water, as a fuel source, provides a flexible and stable power supply, unaffected by changing market conditions (Liu, 2014). Wolfson (2014) described hydroelectric facilities as power stations that generate electricity by harnessing the energy of falling or flowing water. Water is directed through turbines, converting its potential and kinetic energy into rotational motion, which then drives a generator to produce electricity. Hydroelectric power accounts for approximately 16% of the global electricity supply, with major producers including China, Canada, and Brazil. For detailed statistics on hydroelectric power generation in various countries, please refer to the "World Electricity Generation" report.

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to determine the acceptability level of the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source using both descriptive and experimental research approaches.

The descriptive research method involved distributing a survey questionnaire to ninety (90) individuals to gather comprehensive data

on their perceptions regarding the power source's acceptability. The survey assessed the power source in terms of affordability, durability, functionality, and safety. As noted by Mills (2022), a survey typically includes a series of structured questions designed to elicit specific information.

Additionally, an experimental research design was employed. The researchers constructed a system comprising PVC pipes, T-soc fittings, ball valves, elbow fittings, FAPT-u PVC fittings, DC motors, fuses, a capacitor, an energy indicator, a fly hood, a battery, a light, and an inverter. The apparatus was assembled following precise instructions. The experimental procedure involved regulating water pressure, measuring electrical output, and assessing the power source's performance under various conditions. This experimental phase was crucial for product construction and prototype introduction.

Respondents

The researchers utilized the purposive sampling technique. There were three (3) criteria/characteristics considered to choose the respondents of the study. First, they should be households within Barangay Maysan, Barangay Mapulang Lupa, and Barangay Ugong, Valenzuela City. Second, the respondents are using faucets and shower, and lastly, the respondents are the ones paying for their potable water. Purposive sampling technique was used to choose ninety (90) households with Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source to the barangays of Maysan, Mapulang Lupa, and Ugong.

Instrument

The researcher utilizes a questionnaire developed by the researcher and validated by experts in the fields of electronics, electrical engineering, and automation. The questionnaire includes items designed to gather essential data regarding the respondents' profiles, as well as questions related to the acceptability of the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source. The instrument is divided into two sections: the first part collects information about the respondents' profiles, while the second part assesses the acceptability of the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source. Additionally, specialists and consultants provided support and validation for the data analysis and interpretation.

Data Analysis

The statistical data analysis involved calculating percentages, weighted means, chi-square values, and degrees of freedom, employing both Excel and manual computation methods. Percentages were computed to determine the total number of respondents based on their demographic profiles. The weighted mean was utilized to assess the level of acceptability of the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source. To test the hypothesis, the chi-square test was employed to evaluate respondents' perceptions of the product. Degrees of freedom were used in hypothesis testing to determine whether to reject the null hypothesis, based on the final number of variables and data utilized in the experiment concerning the acceptability of the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *The voltage output of the Water Pressure-Driven Power Source on the following pounds per square inch (PSI)*

<i>Pounds per square inch (PSI)</i>	<i>Duration</i>	<i>Voltage Output</i>
20	1 minute	0.02
30	1 minute	0.03
40	1 minute	0.04
50	1 minute	0.05
60	1 minute	0.06
70	1 minute	0.08
80	1 minute	0.09

Table 1 illustrates that the voltage output of the Water Pressure-Driven Power Source increases proportionally with the applied water pressure, measured in pounds per square inch (PSI) over a consistent duration of one minute. At 20 PSI, the power source generated an output voltage of 0.02 volts, while at 30 PSI, the voltage output increased to 0.03 volts. As the pressure continued to rise, the recorded voltage outputs were 0.04 volts at 40 PSI, 0.05 volts at 50 PSI, 0.06 volts at 60 PSI, 0.08 volts at 70 PSI, and 0.09 volts at 80 PSI. These results indicate a direct relationship between water pressure and voltage output, suggesting that higher PSI levels result in greater voltage output. This relationship is crucial for the efficiency of the water pressure-driven power source, as it demonstrates that by adjusting the water pressure, the generated power can be directly influenced.

According to Day (2016), the Lucid Pipe turbine requires flows of at least 20 cfs at 40 psi. Furthermore, each turbine also acts as a pressure reduction valve, reducing head pressure by 1 to 5 psi.

Table 2 shows the charging times for 6-volt, 12-volt, and 24-volt batteries using an improvised water pressure-driven power source. The table illustrates that the improvised power source can fully charge a 6-volt battery in 1 hour at a pressure of 80 pounds per square inch (PSI) with an output voltage of 0.09 volts per minute. The 6-volt battery can also be fully charged in 1 hour and 2 minutes at a pressure of 70 PSI with an output voltage of 0.08 volts per minute. Additionally, it can be fully charged in 1 hour and 7 minutes at a pressure of 60 PSI with an output voltage of 0.06 volts per minute. Furthermore, the 6-volt battery can be fully charged in 2 hours at a

pressure of 50 PSI with an output voltage of 0.05 volts per minute. It can also be fully charged in 2 hours and 5 minutes at a pressure of 40 PSI with an output voltage of 0.04 volts per minute. Moreover, the 6-volt battery can be fully charged in 3 hours and 4 minutes at a pressure of 30 PSI with an output voltage of 0.03 volts per minute. Finally, it can be completely charged in 5 hours at a pressure of 20 PSI with an output voltage of 0.02 volts per minute.

Table 2. *The fully charge of 6v, 12v, and 24v batteries using the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source*

Batteries	Pounds per square inch (PSI)	Voltage	Duration
6V	20	0.02/min	5 hours
	30	0.03/min	3hrs and 4 minutes
	40	0.04/min	2hrs and 5 minutes
	50	0.05/min	2 hours
	60	0.06/min	1hr and 7 minutes
	70	0.08/min	1hr and 2minutes
	80	0.09/min	1 hour
	12V	20	0.02/min
30		0.03/min	6hrs and 7 minutes
40		0.04/min	5 hours
50		0.05/min	4 hours
60		0.06/min	3hrs and 4 minutes
70		0.08/min	2hrs and 5 minutes
80		0.09/min	2hrs and 3 minutes
24V	20	0.02/min	20 hours
	30	0.03/min	13hrs and 4 minutes
	40	0.04/min	10 hours
	50	0.05/min	8 hours
	60	0.06/min	6hrs and 7 minutes
	70	0.08/min	5 hours
	80	0.09/min	4hrs and 5 minutes

The 12-volt battery can be fully charged in 2 hours and 3 minutes at a pressure of 80 PSI with an output voltage of 0.09 volts per minute. It can also be fully charged in 2 hours and 5 minutes at a pressure of 70 PSI with an output voltage of 0.08 volts per minute. The 12-volt battery requires 3 hours and 4 minutes to fully charge at a pressure of 60 PSI with an output voltage of 0.08 volts per minute. Additionally, it can be fully charged in 4 hours at a pressure of 50 PSI with an output voltage of 0.05 volts per minute. The 12-volt battery can also be fully charged in 5 hours at a pressure of 40 PSI with an output voltage of 0.04 volts per minute. Moreover, it can be fully charged in 6 hours and 7 minutes at a pressure of 30 PSI with an output voltage of 0.03 volts per minute. Lastly, the 12-volt battery can be fully charged in 10 hours at a pressure of 20 PSI with an output voltage of 0.02 volts per minute. The 24-volt battery can be fully charged in 4 hours and 5 minutes at a pressure of 80 pounds per square inch (PSI) with an output voltage of 0.09 volts per minute. It can also be fully charged in 5 hours at 70 PSI with an output voltage of 0.08 volts per minute. Additionally, it takes 6 hours and 7 minutes to fully charge the 24-volt battery at 60 PSI, resulting in an output voltage of 0.06 volts per minute. The battery can also be fully charged in 8 hours at 50 PSI, with a voltage output of 0.05 volts per minute. Furthermore, it can be fully charged in 10 hours at 40 PSI with an output voltage of 0.04 volts per minute. Finally, the battery can fully charge in 13 hours and 4 minutes at 30 PSI, with an output voltage of 0.03 volts per minute. It can also completely charge in 20 hours at 20 PSI, yielding a voltage output of 0.02 volts per minute.

In similar vein, According to Goyal (2023), the charging efficiency of a 6-volt battery using an innovative wind-driven power source for tricycles powered also by dynamo improves with increasing tricycle speed. At 20 kph, the battery takes 7 hours and 10 minutes to fully charge, with an output voltage of 0.014 volts. At 30 kph, the charging time reduces to 4 hours and 46 minutes, with an output voltage of 0.021 volts. At 40 kph, the battery charges in 3 hours and 35 minutes, providing an output of 0.047 volts. At the highest speed of 50 kph, the battery fully charges in 2 hours and 52 minutes, with an output voltage of 0.035 volts. This indicates that the wind-driven power source charges the battery more rapidly as the tricycle's speed increases.

On the other hand, the water pressure-driven power source demonstrates that water pressure is a key factor in determining faster charging times, it is contrasted with the influence of wind speed. Higher water pressure (PSI) leads to quicker charging for all three types of batteries, with the charging time varying based on both the battery's voltage and the PSI applied.

Table 3 presents the perceived acceptability of the improvised water pressure-driven power source based on respondents' evaluations of affordability, durability, functionality, and safety. Affordability received a weighted mean of 3.99, interpreted as acceptable. Durability achieved a weighted mean of 4.02, also interpreted as acceptable. Functionality garnered a weighted mean of 4.09, interpreted as acceptable as well. Safety received a weighted mean of 3.99, interpreted as acceptable.

Overall, the four indicators yielded a general weighted mean of 4.02, indicating that the product is perceived as acceptable by the respondents.

Table 3. *Summary of the Level of Acceptability of Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source as Perceived by the Respondents*

Indicators	Average Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Affordability	3.99	Acceptable
Durability	4.02	Acceptable
Functionality	4.09	Acceptable
Safety	3.99	Acceptable
Grand Weighted Total	4.02	Acceptable

The respondents expressed that the water pressure-driven power source is highly functional and durable. The survey results suggest that this improvised power source could serve as an efficient energy solution in the specific areas where the study was conducted. Additionally, the findings highlight that the product is affordable, as the materials needed can be acquired at a low cost to generate power. Safety assessments conducted with various respondents confirmed that the product poses no harm to users. This invention demonstrates the potential to provide low-cost, environmentally friendly electricity without reliance on harmful power sources.

Similarly, the wind-driven power source for tricycles by Goyal (2023) demonstrates high level of acceptability, with average ratings of 4.73 for appearance, 4.7 for functionality, 4.53 for safety, and 4.9 for portability. The overall acceptability mean is 4.72, indicating that respondents find the power source functional, safe, portable, and well-designed. In contrast, the water pressure-driven power source was rated as generally acceptable (overall mean of 4.02) in terms of affordability, durability, functionality, and safety but did not receive as high ratings as the wind-driven option. The wind-driven power source appears to be more advantageous, especially for tricycles, as wind is abundant and more accessible, which explains its high level of acceptability. The water pressure-driven power source received only an "acceptable" rating, likely due to the limited availability of water and the challenge of maintaining sufficient pressure for generating electricity, despite its potential usefulness. However, the water pressure-driven power source is viewed by respondents as a clean and sustainable alternative energy source.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the maximum and fastest charging times for the water pressure-driven power source were 1 hour for a 6-volt battery, 2 hours and 3 minutes for a 12-volt battery, and 4 hours and 5 minutes for a 24-volt battery, all at a PSI of 80, with an output voltage of 0.09 volts per minute. In contrast, the minimum and slowest charging times were 5 hours for a 6-volt battery, 10 hours for a 12-volt battery, and 20 hours for a 24-volt battery, all at a PSI of 20, with an output voltage of 0.02 volts per minute. The improvised water pressure-driven power source was deemed acceptable by the participants in terms of affordability, durability, and functionality.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researchers formulated the following recommendations. Future researchers are encouraged to introduce the product to areas with limited access to the power grid to increase cost-effectiveness by leveraging its renewable energy source. They should also explore alternative materials or designs to enhance durability and functionality while conducting cost-benefit analyses to improve affordability. Additionally, it is important for future researchers to emphasize the significance of rigorous safety testing to address any concerns, ultimately fostering greater acceptability among potential users. Incorporating the use of a water tank to improve water flow efficiency and a water pump to increase pressure is also recommended. Future researchers should prioritize enhancing the functionality and durability of the Improvised Water Pressure-Driven Power Source to maximize its efficiency and sustainability. Furthermore, it is essential that safety and compliance with local regulations are prioritized when implementing water pressure-driven power systems. Focusing on these aspects not only ensures safety but also provides valuable insights for optimizing performance and achieving success with the improvised power source.

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